

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE PROBLEM OF THE SPECIFICITY OF THE HUMANITIES

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Abstract

The article considers the changes taking place in the sphere of humanitarian cognition in connection with the spread of modern media. These transformations are based, first of all, on a new image of man, formulated in philosophical and interdisciplinary discussions. The analysis of the phenomenon of "digital humanities" reveals the main directions of modern epistemological and methodological research.

Keywords: digital humanities, modern media, epistemology, research programmes.

The problem of the specificity of the humanities has developed in various dimensions since the late 18th century. The rapid growth of humanities knowledge, leading to a gradual liberation from "metaphysical" assumptions, has strengthened scientists in their quest for self-determination. The demarcation of boundaries both within thematically and methodologically close fields (such as linguistics and literary studies) and in general with respect to natural and philosophical knowledge has strongly influenced the formation and shaping of the disciplinary matrix of the humanities and social sciences during the 19th and 20th centuries. The processes of "demarcation" led to the transformation of ideas about their own subject matter, methods, and forms of studying human, cultural, and social reality. It is worth noting that naturalism and cultural-centrism were singled out as the most common paradigmatic guidelines in the process of discussions both within the sciences themselves and within different philosophical movements, from positivism to philosophy of life. It was they who set the space for possible development, both in the direction of searching for the ideals of the humanities and social sciences, which increasingly revealed a tendency towards convergence, and in defining the goals and tasks of cognitive activity. In the context of the self-determination of the "Spiritual Sciences", a "demarcation" from the body of scientific and mathematical knowledge was of the utmost importance. The ideology of this process ranged from stark confrontation to the greatest possible fusion.

Meanwhile, the emergence of different methodological programs has opened a new problem field for philosophers and scientists, associated with the need to revise the basic epistemological categories such as knowledge, truth, rationality, ideals and norms of scientific knowledge. The new directions of epistemology that emerged in the twentieth century, in one way or another, were connected with the need to include socio-humanitarian knowledge in the general scientific context. The "linguistic", "interpretative", "communicative" and "anthropological" turns in the sociohumanitarian sciences not only reflected the interdisciplinarity of research carried out in the second half of the 20th century, but set new forms of interaction between science and philosophy.

In the end. XX - beginning. XXI centuries the problem of specificity of socio-humanitarian knowledge in a sense unexpectedly enough for the scientific community itself was actualized in connection with formation of media-reality in which being in the media becomes an inherent attribute of modern man's being. New ways of knowledge representation and dissemination, transformations of everyday practices, and visualisation of the information space lead to significant changes not only in the subject field, but also in the methodology of modern humanitarian research. The basic principles of the new disciplinary scientific complex that is rapidly developing before our eyes, which has been named "digital humanities", are now becoming the subject of epistemological analysis. It is worth specifically mentioning that it is not only about the use of computer technology in working with cultural contexts, as it is often understood.

The term "humanities computing" is used to refer to this, in fact more of a "technological" trend, in a somewhat awkward way. Its emergence has an exact date (1949) and is associated with the creation of the "index verborum, an index of all words of the corpus of texts by Thomas Aquinas and other medieval philosophers counting up to eleven million words of the medieval Latin" [7, p.38]. Thus, starting from the middle of the 20th century, the use of new computing technologies enhanced the possibilities of humanitarian research of texts of different nature, helped to establish new research practices, and substantially eased the process of solving the problems, which required considerable efforts and time for data processing. It was supposed that source data could be formalized and become material available for computer processing and further computational manipulations. But using the opportunities of information environment till a certain moment occurred in those fields where there were already laid some methodological grounds and, what is equally important, the circle of quantifiable parameters was formed, and also the procedures of their meaningful interpretation was prescribed. The situation began to change radically with the emergence and formation of a "media reality" that exists according to specific laws, the identification of which in itself is a very non-trivial research task. Such a state of affairs has already been called "media

turn" in philosophical literature. Meanwhile, the emergence of the "new media", the rapid spread of their influence on various aspects of political, social, and everyday life, and the "reset" of the cultural matrix of modernity are leading to significant changes in the structure of humanitarian research. The complex nature of the studied phenomena, traditionally described within the framework of linguistic, historical, and art history discourses, requires both philosophical and methodological reflection and the revision of some fundamental provisions of the "spirit sciences". Problems arise whose solution is connected with the reformatting of the research space, as new images of humanitarian knowledge are formed in "frontier" areas, revealing new similarities and differences.

An analysis of the development of the sociohumanitarian sciences shows rather convincingly that a certain "human image," which includes not only the most general ideas about its nature, but also implicit assessments, moral judgments, ideals, and norms, always emerges behind scientific research. Such an image serves as a kind of pre-understanding, which in many respects sets the direction of further scientific research. Reflexive efforts to formulate this image, which is an implicit precondition of "the sciences of spirit", usually take place within philosophical discourse, and then penetrate into private scientific and interdisciplinary practices. If we try to capture the general mood of contemporary debates, it can obviously be most accurately defined as eschatological. The words of the philosopher E. Sioran, spoken in the 1970s, could best express the extremely widespread disillusionment with the human being, who appears in an extremely unfavourable light today. "After all his brilliant conquests and accomplishments, man begins to go out of fashion. Passing off a war against himself as a proud rebellion, the creature has shaken its own foundations... The innermost depths have been struck, rotten to the roots. After becoming transparent to himself, man is no longer capable of any action, of any "creativity". Having gained an epiphany, having lost his naivety, he will be completely exhausted". [6, p. 155-156] Such signs of human existence today are available for public scrutiny, come to the surface from human existence in personal space thanks to the "new" media. In a certain sense, we can say that the contemporary situation turns out to be a traumatic experience of the individual's self, experienced not post factum, but here and now.

The ways in which the media exploit the freedom of expression are understandably perplexing. It is hard not to agree with the master of paradoxes S. It is hard to disagree with the master of paradoxes S. Žižek, who, in his characteristic manner, polemicalises with the majority of researchers who tend to sound the alarm about the loss of private space by modern man. "This platitude must be answered with the opposite assertion: what is disappearing is public space in the true sense. The person who posts naked pictures of himself or shares intimate information and indecent dreams on the internet is not an exhibitionist at all: the exhibitionist invades public space, whereas those who post naked pictures of themselves online remain in their private space, simply expanding it to include other people. The

foreseeable outcome of such expansion is an increasing moral emptiness." [1, c. 14]

Fears about human and cultural transformations are expressed today not only by philosophers and representatives of the humanities, but also by those who are usually considered to be ideological "technocrats" directly connected with the construction of the media environment and its carriers. Thus, the author of the term "virtual reality", D. Lanier, one of the most famous practical programmers, in his address to contemporary media users, writes: "We are increasing your capacity with remote eyes and ears (webcams and mobile phones) and expanding memory (a sea of details on the Web). "We interfere with your philosophy by manipulating your cognitive experience directly rather than indirectly through persuasion. It only takes a small group of engineers to create a technology capable of changing the future of human perception at an incredible speed." [2, p. 17] A media utopia behind which a new image of a human being is clearly visible becomes not only a theoretical problem but also has quite practical consequences whose reflection is taking place on various "discussion platforms". However, there are optimists like the ideologists of the "digital generation", K. Nordström and J. Ridderstrølle, who claim that never before has humanity: "There have been no such great opportunities for self-actualization. We can all become as unique as our fingerprints and as peculiar as we were meant to be from the very beginning. Scholars of the world believe that we are entering a "me, me, me" type of society, selfish and self-centred. But individualism is not necessarily about selfishness - rather, it is about the self-realisation and integrity of each individual." [5, c. 147]

One way or another, the global transformation of the image of man behind the subject matter of the modern socio-humanitarian sciences turns out to be not only a basis for evaluation and prediction, but also an object of epistemological reflection. The unbelievable "transparency" of the media "world" for the former culture provides researchers with an immense wealth of "empirical" material. Such possibilities present themselves as a serious challenge that calls for a reconsideration of established practices. For example, L. Manovich suggests a rather interesting strategy for dealing with "old" and "new" research agendas. "In addition to theorizing about the imagined abstract user (a typical humanities strategy), or using surveys to learn about people's cultural experiences, or ethnography (communication studies) - in addition to all this, we can collect and analyze data about people's actual interactions with software artifacts." [4, p. 205-206] The only thing confusing about this statement is the problem of the methodological basis for "collecting and analysing" data. Meanwhile, it seems to us that the idea of mutual complementarity of different research programmes in the "digital humanities" can be quite productive if there are discussion platforms that exploit the possibilities of interactivity in the field of scientific inquiry.

Thus, we are faced with an important problem related to the need for epistemological analysis and discussion of the foundations of emerging methodological paradigms and research programmes. The interactivity

and intermediality of the objects encountered by media researchers, their principal individuality and uniqueness, make the problem of the relation between the nomothetic and the ideographic in the methodological settings of sociohumanitarian cognition relevant again. The development of a wide range of possibilities associated with the use of information and communication environment in scientific research of culture and society, in turn, transforms the ways of representation and interpretation of the results of scientific search. For example, the increase of visual component in the information flow of modern media has a significant impact on the formulation of research tasks and ways of their achievement. It should be noted that the strategies of interpreting the visual, as opposed to the verbal, have been on the periphery of scientific and philosophical interest until recently. Understanding the specifics of the process of "translating" the actually existing objects of socio-humanitarian research into digital format, in our opinion, requires the development of new hermeneutic procedures that take into account the practices of interaction between the visual and the verbal in various discourses (from political to everyday life).

The interaction and mutual influence of methodologies and technologies of scientific work with huge amounts of data stored in the global "archive" are also among the most important problems related to the challenges of our time. The development and use of special technological procedures for searching, processing and representation of scientific information turns out to be closely related to the methodology set by the initial settings of the researcher. As L. Manovich points out, interactive media present the modern researcher with a non-trivial task. Their very structure forces scholars: "to engage in endless arrays of data" [4, p. 209]. In this case, the methodology of science is not only closely linked to the technology of working with digital content, but directly dependent on it. And this dependence will manifest itself at all stages - from the task setting, to the choice of search strategy, to the process of interpretation of the results. This is a challenge that humanities scholars have not yet had to face, even given the experience of "humanities computing". But the challenge is not just about analysing actual research. Reflecting on the future, we are forced to recognise that ways of preserving historical and cultural heritage also turn out to be a problem not only of a specifically practical nature but also require theoretical reflection. For

example, G. Lubbe accurately points out that "for reasons of principle, as the dynamics of civilizational evolution increase, the predictability of those interests that will guide those who will turn to the actualization of the past in the future decreases. This means that the role of chance in the process of shaping the archival tradition is increasing. So far, only in a very preliminary way is it possible to understand how the rapidly growing part of electronic communication in the totality of communication as a whole will affect the chances of its selection and historical reception". [3, p. 412] If we do not want to leave the future researcher alone with a random and de-hierarchized set of interactive media documents, we have to work out not only new technologies of archiving, but also take care of clarifying their methodological foundations.

It is no exaggeration to say that the challenges posed by the emergence and proliferation of modern media give a new dimension to the development of socio-humanitarian sciences. For some time now, primarily because of a certain methodological "exhaustion" of hermeneutic, psychoanalytic, Marxist, semiotic, structuralist and poststructuralist research programmes, the question of the necessity and social value of humanitarian and social knowledge was quite acute. For the most part, scholars and philosophers have had to resort to some rather vague assurances about the necessity of the humanities for preserving and developing the humanistic potential of culture. Today, a space of fundamentally new possibilities is opening up for the humanities, which will greatly help to "reformat" research strategies for understanding not only the past, but also the future.

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